

Variation of Phase Space Cells in Statistical Mechanics

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Phase space cells and the counting of states of particles distributed in phase space seems to be important in statistical mechanics because calculations of the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions follow from the maximization of factorial arrangements of particles in phase space cells subject to constraints on total energy and particle number. In particular, $g(i)! / [n(e_i)! (g_i - n(e_i))!]$ is applied to fermions and $(g_i + n(e_i))! / [n(e_i)! (g_i - 1)!]$ to bosons. For $g_i \gg n(e_i)$ one obtains the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution in both cases. In (1), changes to phase space cell sizes are considered for the Maxwell-Boltzmann case by considering changes to the MB distribution. $\exp(-e/T)$ is replaced by $\exp(-f(e))$ with $f(e) = e/T + e^*e(1-q)$ where q is an unknown constant close to 1. This is compared to expansions of $N \ln(N) - \sum_i n(e_i) \ln(e_i)$ about the equilibrium solution $n(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$ and then it is argued that the number of arrangements equals the phase space volume divided by cell size to the power of N , the number of particles. (There is an additional $N!$ to account for identical particles). In this note, we first consider changes to the MB $n(e_i)$ from ((1)) for $g_i > n(e_i)$ out of curiosity. Next, we consider a microcanonical approach for the calculation of the number of states of an MB gas and perform an expansion beyond a linear e_i . The result yields an e^*e correction term with b given instead of being represented by the parameter $(1-q)$.

In Between Quantum and Classical Phase Space Cells

In a previous note (2), we argued that phase space resolution is important for determining quantum and classical distributions. We argued that for an MB gase, all phase space points (i.e. all momentum and position vectors) may be resolved and so $g(e_i) = dV d^3p / h^3$ is very large compared with $n(e_i)$. Furthermore, in the classical regime, one usually deals with large volumes compared with the quantum case. For the quantum case, the uncertainty relationship destroys some of the resolution of phase space points. For example, one may have slightly different momentum vector directions, but these are considered the same in an argument given by Feynman (3) used to obtain: $P(n \text{ indistinguishable bosons in } e_i) = n! P(n \text{ distinguishable bosons in } e_i)$. This relationship leads to an enhancement in the probability of $1+f(e_i)$ of scattering into a state with $f(e_i)$ bosons. This in turn leads to a reaction balance equation for $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ of: $f(e_1)[1+f(e_3)]f(e_2)[1+f(e_4)] = f(e_3)[1+f(e_3)]f(e_4)[1+f(e_2)]$ from which the BE distribution may be derived.

Furthermore, in using ((1)) to obtain the Bose-Einstein distribution, $g(e_i)$ and $n(e_i)$ are treated as being on the same order (or at least $n(e_i)$ is not much smaller than $n(e_i)$). Thus, $g(e_i)$ which represents the degeneracy or number of degenerate phase space cells with energy e_i is a smaller number than for the classical case where all phase space points are resolvable. To obtain the MB distribution, one may replace $g_i + n(e_i)$ in ((1)) by g_i and a similar result holds for the Fermi-Dirac case. Out of curiosity, we consider here the distribution which results from $g_i > n(e_i)$, but not to the extent that one drops $n(e_i)$.

Consider ((1)) converted using Stirling's approximation:

$$(g_i+n_i)[\ln(g_i+n_i)] - n_i \ln(n_i) \quad \text{Here } g_{i-1} \text{ approx} = g_i$$

Next, expand $\ln(g_i+n_i)$ approx = $\ln(g_i) + n_i/g_i + \dots$

and, vary with respect to the constraints $\sum n_i = N$ and $\sum e_i n_i = E_{\text{total}}$.

$$-\ln(n_i) + 2n_i/g - b_1 e_i - b_2 + \ln(g_i) = 0$$

n_i/g is very small so to first approximation: $n_{i,0} = C g_i \exp(-b_1 e_i)$

Next, assume $n_i = n_{i,0} + d$ where d is small. Then:

$$-d/n_{i,0} + 2n_{i,0}/g = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad d = 2 n_{i,0} * n_{i,0} / g_i$$

Thus, $n_i = C g_i \exp(-b_1 e_i) [1 + 2 C \exp(-b_1 e_i)] \quad ((3))$

$g_i = dV d^3p / h^3$ and C and b_1 may be found through $\sum n_i = N$ and $\sum e_i n_i = E_{\text{total}}$

If one takes the limit of the Bose-Einstein distribution $f(e_i) = 1 / [\exp((e_i - \mu)/T) - 1]$ for $\exp((e_i - \mu)/T) \gg 1$, one simply obtains the usual MB distribution.

Microcanonical Maxwell-Boltzmann Approach

In a previous note (2), we argued that one may approximate a microcanonical scenario of a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas using:

$$M(E/a) = \ln[\text{Number of macrostates}] = \ln\left\{ \frac{(E/a + V)!}{V! (E/a)!} \right\}$$

E/a is the smallest amount of energy which may be exchanged during a scattering interaction, with $a = \text{constant}$.

Here we do not sum over N particles, but rather over V cells. Otherwise, "T", the temperature equals E/N which does not account for momentum phase space.

To calculate the probability of finding a particle with energy e_i , one may calculate:

$$\ln(P(e_i)) = M(E/a - e_i/a) - M(E/a) \quad ((4))$$

No maximization with respect to constraints is required. To first order, ((4)) yields the usual MB result, but for $e_i \ll E$ which is the situation for large particle number systems. For small particle number systems, it seems that if e_i is of the order of E , one no longer has an MB distribution. The objective here is to expand ((4)) in terms of e_i and to include second order e_i terms:

$$\ln(P(e_i)) = C(E) - e/a \ln(E/a - V) - (e/a)^2 1/(E/a - V) + e/a \ln(E/a) - e^2/(E/a) \quad ((5))$$

Thus, $P(e_i)$ is of the form: $D \exp(-b_1 e_i + b_2 e_i^2)$ ((6))

$$\text{With } b_2 = 1/(E/a - V) - 1/(E/a)$$

Thus, there is an exact result for b_2 .

If the second order correction is not included: $P(e_i) = D \exp(-b_1 e_i)$ which is the Maxwell-Boltzmann result which may be fixed using $\sum_i P(e_i) = 1$ and $\sum_i e_i P(e_i) = E_{\text{total}}$.

We next try to compare the above results with those given in (1). The point seems to be that not only is the distribution $P(e_i)$ changed, but in (1) it is argued that this means the phase space cell size is also changed.

Phase Space Cell Changes Following (1)

In (1), it is noted one may maximize $\ln(W_o) = \ln\{ N! / [\text{Product over } i n_i!] \}$ subject to $\sum_i n_i = N$ and $\sum_i e_i n_i = E_{\text{total}}$ to obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. Here W_o is the number of arrangements. It is argued that one may keep correction terms beyond the equilibrium result to obtain:

$W_q = N \ln(N) - \sum_i n_i \ln(n_i)$ expanded about $n_o(e_i)$ (the equilibrium result) to obtain:

$$n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i)) - (\delta n(e_i)) (\text{expression 1}) - [\delta n(e_i)]^2 (.5/n_o(e_i)) \quad ((6))$$

with expression 1 = 0 because of the maximum condition.

W_q is the number of macrostates (arrangements) associated with a full $n(e_i)$, while W_o is the number of arrangements associated with $n_o(e_i)$ i.e. the MB distribution.

Next, one may expand $n(e_i)$ in powers of e_i i.e. $n(e_i) = n_o(e_i) \exp(-.5 e_i^2 (1-q))$ ((7))

q is a parameter close to 1, but unknown. Using $\sum_i n_i(e_i) = N$ and ((7)), it is found in (1) that:

$$n(e_i) = n_o(e_i) [1 + 15/8 (1-q) - .5 (1-q) (e_i/T)^2] \quad \text{so } \delta n(e_i) = [15/8 (1-q) - .5 (1-q) (e_i/T)^2]$$

Thus, $\sum_i [\delta n_o(e_i)]^2 \cdot (1/n_o(e_i))$ may be evaluated as: $45/4 N (1-q)^2$.

Then: $W_q/W_o = \exp[-45/8 N (1-q)^2(1-q)]$. The main idea of (1) is that:

$$W_q/W_o = (\text{Phase space } q) / (\text{Phase space } o) \cdot [\text{Cell } o / \text{Cell } q]^N \quad ((8))$$

Thus, if the phase space volume for q and o are argued to remain constant, then the cell size (which is h^3 for the “ o ” case) is said to change for the q case, by $\exp[-45/8 (1-q)^2(1-q)]$. Later in (1), this expression is enhanced, but we stop here.

Microcanonical Situation and Cell Size

In (1), a correction to the MB distribution (of order $(1-q)e_i \cdot e_i$) is argued to correspond to a change in the size of a phase space cell. By changing the cell size, and leaving the phase space volume unchanged, one obtains a different number of arrangements.

For the microcanonical approach, one uses $dV d^3p$ as a phase space volume (small piece of the volume) for a single particle and (h^3) as the cell size (for a single particle). This corresponds to the MB distribution.

If one considers higher order corrections to the MB distribution which arise naturally in the microcanonical approach (i.e. $n_o(1-q)$ needs to be added), then it seems one would argue that this change in the MB distribution is due to the phase space cell size changing.

Is there another way to consider this matter? Consider two particle elastic scattering in an MB gas. Then:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad \text{and} \quad f(e_1) f(e_2) = f(e_3) f(e_4)$$

Taking \ln of the latter and linking to the former yields the MB distribution without any correction terms. Thus, the correction terms from the microcanonical approach may be related to correlations linked to phase space cell size in the same manner in which $g(e_i)$ (the degeneracy) becomes the driving idea in the Bose-Einstein and Fermi-Dirac cases.

For the BE and FD cases, h^3 does not change, but there seems to be lower resolution, i.e. some momentum vectors pointing in slightly different directions are considered to point in the same direction (as argued by Feynman in (2)). In fact, in the BE and FD cases, changes occur in the phase space cells such that the one no longer has a canonical distribution, but a grand canonical one, in which one can only speak of an average number of particles $n(e_i)$ assigned to each degenerate cell.

For the microcanonical approach considered in this note, one may immediately obtain an $e_i \cdot e_i$ correction term without having to use a $(1-q)$ parameter where q is close to 1.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we note that reaction balance leads to exactly $f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T)$. A microcanonical approach introduced in (2), however, leads to $e_i * e_i$ correction terms i.e. $f(e_i) = C \exp(-e_i/T + b e_i * e_i)$. Thus, one may argue as in (1), that perhaps the phase space cell size is changing if $dV d^3p$ remains the same. This seems to match ideas presented in (1) which deal with the changing of phase space cell size due to changes in the MB distribution. The main point of this note is that the microcanonical approach allows for an immediate calculation of the altered MB distribution without the insertion of a $(1-q)$ (q close to 1) factor as in (1).

References

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